

New Trends for Developing Skills in Higher Education

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Abstract

India is fast developing country. From Primary sector of agriculture, we are moving to secondary sector of manufacturing, construction & also territory sector of trade, transport & finance. India has the second highest population of the working age (15-59 years) individual in the world. The skill set of this population group plays a critical role in the growth of the country. In India education plays a vital role to built skill based society of the 21st century. It is the quality of education that decides the quality of human resources of the country. The intent of the present paper is to analysis the status of contemporary education and to examine the role of government with respect to skill development. The study answers the current position of skill development & higher education and the opportunities available to learners for skill development. The study also answers the way forward and give possible suggestions.

KEYWORDS: Contemporary Education, skill development

Introduction:

India is fast developing country. From primary sector of agriculture, we are moving to secondary sector of manufacturing, construction and also territory sector of trade, transport and finance. India's workforce is second largest in the world after china. Over 65% of India's large population is below 35 years of age below and it has 50% of its population the age of 25.

Working age group of 15-59 years is increasing steadily. Its population pyramid is expected to "bulge" across the 15-59 age group over the next decade. It is further estimates that the average age of population in India by 2020 will be 29 years as against 40 years in USA, 46 years in Europe and 47 years in Japan and 37 years in China.

Increasing population was earlier drawback but now the same has turned to be an asset of the nation. Government has realized that labour workforce is not skilled. To contribute to the growth of economy, we need to have skilled workforce which can be available by vocational & training system. Skilled workers increase the efficiency and flexibility of the labour market and can be move sustainable growth.

In India, only education plays a vital role to build skill based society of the 21st century. If a nation is system, education is the heart of it. Education empowers the nation. Education is important input for the growth of the nation. Properly planned education can increase national gross products, cultural richness, build positive attitude towards technology, increase efficiency and effectiveness of the governance. So every government is now committed to provide the facilities that are required for educating a child right from the beginning. As compared to western economics where there is a burden of an ageing population. India has a unique 20-25 years window of opportunity

called the "demographic dividend", means India has a higher proportion of working age population.

Objective:

In this paper our basic concern is first to study the present scenario of India on skill & education second to examine role of government higher education for skill development and third to suggest possible solutions or ways forward.

Methodology:

The study is based on secondary data collected from reputed articles of research journals, books, prominent sites, report sets relevant to higher education and skill development in India.

India's Scenario on Skill and Education:

The education and skill development scenario sector broadly comprises of school education, higher education & industrial including vocational training. It should be noted that while, in general, 'Skill Development' refers to the larger objective of 'equipping an individual with marketable skills'. However in recent times 'Skill development' has been largely used in the context of technical/vocational training for the manufacturing/industrial or service sector.

The following figure presents an overview of the structure of the educational and skill development sector in India.

Figure 1: Structure of Education and skill development in India

Higher education system in India compare to developing/developed countries needs substantial improvement. The percentage of students taking higher education is hardly

about 13% where as the same is varying between 28 to 90% across the world. The lowest percent being 28% and the same is as high as 90% in developed countries.

The drop – out rates of educational institutions was estimated to be 50% in the age group of 5-14 years and 68% after 15 years of age and in contrast to this the participation rate of the workforce rises rapidly after 14 years of age. 38% of India workforce is illiterate and 36% has an education level of middle & higher level.

India is among the top countries in which employers are facing difficulty in filling up the jobs. Globally, the number of countries, where in the percentage of employers experiencing difficulties in filling up job vacancies have been rising. As far as India is concerned, it is on 7th position in facing difficulty in filling job.

Fig. 2 : Percentage having difficulties in filling the jobs globally

For India, The difficulty to fill up the job is 58% which is above the global standard of 38% in 2015. The world economy forum indicates that only a little bit of percentage of the total Indian professionals are considered employable by the organized sector.

Comparing with 2014, the proportion of employable persons decreases from 64% to 58%. Employers are having major difficulties in filling jobs in Accounting & finance staff, IT personnel, Secretaries, PAs, Teachers, Engineers, Marking/Public Relations Management/Executive, legal staff researchers. On the other hand, higher education sector has witnessed a tremendous increase in the number of university/university level Institutions & colleges since independence – There are 47 central universities, 367 state university, 123 deemed university, 227 private universities in India. These data indicates that India now has the largest higher education system in the world in terms of the number of Institutions, and the second largest in terms of the number of students. Though India has one of the largest education systems in the world, employability of the graduates is often quoted as one of the biggest challenges the country faces today. With current and expected economic growth, more than 75% of the new job opportunities are expected to be skill-based. The current capacity of the skill development programs is 3.1 million. India has target of skilling 500 million people by 2022. So the government has to put massive effort to form better educational structure especially for skill development sector comprising of industry oriented training. In 2009, the government formulated the national skill development policy that laid the framework for skill development, ensuring that individuals get improved access to skills and knowledge. The policy states the roles and responsibilities of stakeholders, which include the government, industry, trade unions, local governments, civil society institutions and skill providers. The policy lay down following institutional framework comprising:-

- Prime Minister's National Council on Skill Development.
- National Skill Development Co-ordination Board.
- National Skill Development Co-operation (NSDC)

- National Council for Vocational Training (NCVT)

The policy provides for having a separate institutional mechanism to plan, implement & monitor the skill development for recognized sector.

Role of government for developing Skill:

Skill Development is the biggest issue for Indian Government. So government is taking initiative and playing a vital role for developing skill. Government gave priority to skill development in twelfth five year plan. The government's plans to set up sector skill councils to prepare students required for training programs. The industries are also productively taking steps to partner with the government and reduce the skill gap.

In India's Union Budget 2016-17 Hon'ble Finance Minister Shri Arun Jately, mentioned nine focus area of development, including education, skills and job creation for promoting higher education, Shri Jatly proposed to set up a Higher Education Financing Agency with an initial Capital base of Rs. 1000 Crore. For skill training, the budget is marked Rs. 1,700 crore, which will be used to set up 1,500 multi-skill training institutions across the country. In 2014 government has passed the amendment to the existing act known as 'Apprentices Bill, 2014' to increase the number of skilled man power. According to the Bill the industry with flexibility to hire apprentices will have 2.5-10 percent of the total work force as apprentices. Prime Minister Narendra Modi in June 2014 announced the creation of a first-ever separate Ministry of skill Development and entrepreneurship to promote entrepreneurship and skill development.

The Ministry of Human Resource and Development (MHRD) governs the polytechnic institutions offering diploma level courses under various disciplines such as engineering and technology, pharmacy, architecture, applied arts and crafts and Hotel Management. MHRD has also introduced vocational education from class IX onwards besides it central Ministries is also playing important role for developing skill. There are 21 Ministers under the central government working for the purpose of skill development.

The National Skill Development Corporation Indian (NSDC) is Public private partnership organisation that was incorporated in 2009 under the national skill policy. National Skill Development Coordination Board NSDC is set up on a PPP model. The board formulates policies and programs on National Skill Development under the ambit of Prime Minister's Council. The agency planned to establish 1500 new ITIs and 5000 Skill development centers. The National Vocational Education Qualification Frame work will be formed for an integrated skill development infrastructure. This framework is for affiliations and accreditation of vocational education and training system.

Some of other key initiatives of the government are as follows:

- Establishment of new ITI's in under served regions and the existing ITI's being upgraded to centers of excellence to produce multi-skilled work force of world standards.
- Setting up more polytechnics in the PPP mode & 400 government polytechnics being updated.
- Establishment of 600 rural development & self employment training institutes.
- To set up virtual skill development resources linking 50000 skill development centers.

Recommendations and way forward:

India as a whole, realizes the complete seriousness and importance of possessing a skilled workforce. As highlighted above, there are several programs and schemes

initiated these issues. Besides it there are some following specific measures which can be taken by various stake holders, government & educational institutes.

1. Government can launched National Campaign and promote skilling for creating awareness.
2. Awareness on need for skilling should be taken up in mission mode.
3. Skill India logo to be used.
4. Encourage students to opt for vocational stream in school.
5. Vocational Education needs to be integrated with general educations in colleges.
6. There has to be seamless facilitation from secondary to higher education if a student chooses to study vocational courses.
7. The Higher education policy needs to be in line with present and projected employment and there should be a focus on revising the curriculum and offering relevant new courses.

Conclusion:

The Indian Government has laid a special focus on expanding and improving the skill education and training in the country. The new policy on skill development and Entrepreneurship contains several initiatives which, if implemented earnestly, will go a long way in minimizing the demand – supply gap and challenges related to skill mismatch with requirements.

Skilling has certainly seen a growing focus from government and other stake holders & we hope it would have sustained attention from decision maker. In present time occupational patterns are changing. Employment demands are shifting towards higher skill categories. Hence it is necessary for India to move up the skill ladder and produce a large number of people with higher education and training for knowledge work. For these three major areas to be focused to ensure that our education system is sustainable and meets global standard:

- ✓ Quality of Education – in terms of infrastructure teachers, accreditation etc.
- ✓ Affordability of Education – ensuring poor and deserving students are not denied of education.
- ✓ Ethics in education avoiding over – commercialization of education.

These three major areas will help India to become, "Knowledge Economy" to promote inclusive growth. It is time to bring in the changes that will give us the momentum to find a place in a global scenario for this Govt. & public both should work hand to hand to support each other & look for the required uplift men of education.

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